

Speculation on the Second Law of Thermodynamics Leading to Discrete Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 28, 2024

In this note, we ask whether the second law of thermodynamics, namely the statement that entropy stays the same or increases if no work/effort is performed leads to the discrete energy levels of a quantum bound state.

We argue that effort/work is required to increase energy and so there is an arrow of time linked with a higher energy state changing to a lower one, which we assume may happen spontaneously. We thus suggest that the lower state must have more entropy.

We begin with the notion that quantum mechanics is linked with both spatial and temporal resolution through $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle. We consider the example of an oscillator and assume some kind of single crest for the ground state, without using the time-independent Schrodinger equation. We then ask: Why cannot one simply increase the base of this crest to allow for all increased energy levels, i.e. have no discrete energy levels. Wavefunctions would then not be orthogonal, but we imagine that one does not have this a priori condition and ask whether one may rule this out using the second law of thermodynamics.

If one could increase the base (and maybe the shape slightly) of a single crest, then as energy increased time resolution \hbar/E would increase, but spatial resolution would decrease. We suggest that spatial resolution behaves in the opposite way to entropy. A decrease in spatial resolution means more entropy for a higher state and so it should not then spontaneously decay into a lower one. The only way to increase the spatial resolution of a higher state is to have better spatial resolution which means adding crests and troughs. This is not an infinitesimal change and so is linked with finite energy changes, hence the discrete energy levels.

In other words, we suggest that the quantum discreteness of energy seems to be a statement of the second law of thermodynamics, namely that work/energy should increase "order" so that spontaneous decay leads to less order in the sense of less spatial resolution. We only consider here entropy in terms of the spatial resolution (and time resolution).

Alternatively, even for a free particle, $\exp(ipx)$, the higher p , the higher order, i.e. the less the entropy. One must, however, perform work to increase p . As a result, the resolution of $\exp(ipx)$ and its energy are linked to entropy. This idea is carried over into the time-independent Schrodinger equation which then yields a new average resolution seen in $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but which then must be linked with higher levels having more spatial resolution. Extra resolution cannot occur unless one has more crests and troughs and this is not an infinitesimal change and so is not linked with $E \rightarrow E+dE$.

Second Law of Thermodynamics

The second law of thermodynamics states loosely that energy stays the same or increases unless one performs work. In other words, a spontaneous physical change should be linked with the same entropy or greater.

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle is associated with the special probabilities (wavefunction) $\exp(-iEt)$ $\exp(ipx)$. These determine temporal and spatial resolutions: \hbar/e and \hbar/p . A free particle may interact through collisions and from the point of view of the single particle its p may increase or decrease, but if one considers a two body interaction, conservation of momentum ensures that the product resolution does not change, so this is consistent with the second law of thermodynamics, i.e.

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(ip_3x) \exp(ip_4x) \text{ with } p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4 \quad ((1))$$

Later, we consider only a single $\exp(ipx)$ and the effects of a change in p .

We then ask whether one may apply the second law of thermodynamics to a quantum bound system.

Quantum Bound System

A quantum bound system, like a classical, may have increasing levels of energy. In particular, one may do work on a system (atom) by absorbing a photon and increase its energy. Such an increased energy state, however, can spontaneously decay, by emitting a photon, hence one does not have time reversal and the higher energy state should have less entropy than a lower one. We suggest that one may approximate entropy by considering spatial resolution. One might argue that one should consider the photon entropy in such a case, but we argue that it is linked with momentum conservation which always occurs so that:

$$\exp(i p_{\text{atom}} x) \exp(ip_{\text{photon}} x) \text{ before} = \exp(i p_{\text{atom}} x) \exp(ip_{\text{photon}} x) \text{ after} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, one may only consider the spatial resolution of the electron in the quantum bound state. We consider the example of an oscillator here and assume a single crest for the ground state resolution. We do not use the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

One may then propose changing this single crest infinitesimally to move from E to $E+dE$. In such a case, one would have discrete energies. As energy increases, $\exp(-iEt)$ shows that temporal resolution increases, i.e. \hbar/E becomes smaller. If one, however, considers the photon as well, then $\exp(-iE_0 t) \exp(-i E_{\text{photon}} t) = \exp(-i E_1 t)$ and so there is no increase in overall temporal resolution.

Spatially, however, the length between the classical turning points $= 2 * \sqrt{2E/k}$ increases and so the spatial resolution decreases. Thus, temporally entropy is remaining constant (if one considers the photon) with an energy increase, but spatially entropy is increasing. One wishes to have entropy increase/stay the same whether one considers time or space. This suggests that one cannot infinitesimally change the crest and that one must increase spatial resolution. The only way to increase spatial resolution is to have more crests and troughs. One starts with a

single crest, then a crest and trough etc. Such a change, however, is not infinitesimal and so should be associated with discrete energy changes.

We note that these ideas apply to the localized region between classical turning points as this is where one has resolution. One has a decaying wavefunction outside these points. The increase in spatial resolution is also key for obtaining orthogonal wavefunctions.

Quantum Free Particles

We next consider the case of quantum free particles. These are not localized (unlike the bound case), but still have spatial and temporal resolutions linked to $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$. Any p and E are allowed. It was already argued that changes to p and E occur in two body scattering or an impulse hit which conserves momentum at least. Thus, spatially the product $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ does not lead to any entropy increase if entropy is linked to overall spatial resolution. As a result, the bound case argument and resolution seem to be linked to a spontaneous decay of a higher energy level to a lower, whereas moving from a low energy to a higher one is linked with work. If one did not have this condition, then it seems that one would not consider the second law of thermodynamics in the first place.

It is, however, possible to obtain the bound wavefunctions by using the time-independent Schrodinger equation which does not seem to be based on entropy or thermodynamics, but rather one average energy and the form $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle. It does, however, lead to higher spatial resolution for higher energy (and orthogonality) as a mathematical property. Even for a free particle, however, increasing spatial resolution leads to higher energy. Given that a bound problem involves an increasing localized region between classical turning points, infinitesimal changes in a wavefunction would be linked with less spatial resolution and hence less average curvature and energy, not more as is required. Thus, it seems that even if one considers only the time-independent Schrodinger equation, the idea of increasing spatial resolution is linked with increasing energy and we argue that this seems to be consistent with the second law of thermodynamics.

We further note that $\exp(ipx)$ is like a probability and so is associated with entropy. We suggest that more spatial resolution is linked with less entropy, i.e. more information and more energy. This same idea seems to be carried over into the time-independent Schrodinger equation which uses an average of $p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$'s and so inherently brings in the idea of entropy through a new average spatial resolution found in $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the discrete energy levels of a quantum bound system follow from the second law of thermodynamics. Even for a free particle, $\exp(ipx)$, the higher p , the higher order, i.e. the less the entropy. One must, however, perform work to increase p . As a result, the resolution of $\exp(ipx)$ and its energy are linked to entropy. This idea is carried over into the time-independent Schrodinger equation which then yields a new average resolution seen in $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but which then must be linked with higher levels having more spatial resolution. Extra resolution cannot occur unless one has more crests and troughs and this is not an infinitesimal change and so is not linked with $E \rightarrow E+dE$.